

SCHOOL OPERATIONS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF K-12 CURRICULUM AND PERFORMANCE OF SCHOOL HEADS IN CALABARZON: BASIS FOR CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

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School Operations in the Implementation of K-12 Curriculum and Performance of School Heads in CALABARZON: Basis for Curriculum Management Framework

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of school operations of elementary school heads in the CALABARZON in the implementation of K-12 curriculum and the level of performance using the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads among five (5) Schools Division Offices in CALABARZON region. This descriptive research integrates quantitative data using validated research-made questionnaire using percentage, mean, two-way ANOVA and Pearson moment of correlation. Most school heads were principal I, with master's degrees, and 6-10 years of experience. Findings revealed that school heads manifested "Best" in school operations and "To a Very Much Extent" in the level of performance, and that there is no significant difference in the school operations and in the level of performance of the school heads. In terms of relationship between the level of school operations and performance it found out that there is a significant relationship between curriculum and instruction and leading strategically. Addressing operational challenges enhances overall school system effectiveness. Elementary School Heads exhibit commitment to delivering an enhanced educational experience. Proactive approaches to leadership, curriculum, accountability, and resource challenges align with the best practices for quality education and improvement.

Keywords: *school operations, performance, school heads*

Introduction

International experience shows that high-quality education results from a school leader's good school operations skills. Leadership as well as a systemwide focus on grooming and supporting school leaders. Countries worldwide are competing globally to attain a knowledge economy, embarking on extensive educational reform to enhance school performance of their respective schools through developing human capital.

Nations worldwide welcome and promote a wide range of educational reforms to meet the demands of education and prepare our school heads, teachers, and learners for the changing world. School leaders should adopt changes in terms of their own educational settings.

K to 12 curriculum is a relevant example that facilitates changes and serves as a standard for primary education both in globally and locally settings. It is standard and competence-based, inclusive, and built on the needs of Filipino learners and the community. The diverse curriculum that, can address learners' needs, and may be adapted to fit specific groups of learners.

In addition, school heads in the K- 12 curriculum anchor on the principal development program of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). A part of the governance and school operations ensures the organization's ability to improve and strategically manage the environment in which teaching and learning occurs. Domain 2 of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH), Managing School Operations and Resources, focuses on the role of school heads in managing school systems and processes. This Domain demonstrates the school leaders' commitment ensuring efficiency, effectiveness, and fairness in functioning to maximize organizational health. At the same time school administrators comprehend and apply laws, policies, guidelines, and issuances about the management of human, financial, and material resources and assist in the establishment of a culture of transparency and accountability in the continuous provision of essential education services in the k-12 curriculum.

In addition, the schools' overall operation is the principals' responsibility as stated in the RA 9155. State statutes outline some of their duties and responsibilities. As school's heads became more accountable for their student's performance on national and state assessments, Principals took on increased responsibility for teaching and learning in their schools.

In a local setting, one of the responsibilities of the school head is to monitor instruction and to improve teaching and learning of the teachers. Effective school leaders put learning at the center of the daily activities in the school. Principals discovered the need to evaluate instruction; and assist teachers as they worked to improve their instructional techniques as their responsibilities changed more effectively and strategically. As a result, school principals play a crucial role in ensuring that all students have access to a supportive and respectful environment (Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads) (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020). The five leadership areas that school leaders must embody demonstrate the characteristics of a twenty-first-century school leader. These include strategic leadership, oversight of school operations and finances, a focus on teaching and learning, self-improvement, and the development of professional networks (Valenzuela & Buenvinida, 2021).

On the other hand, conducted a study focusing on principals' staff personnel administrative strategies for fostering teacher-job satisfaction and discovered that principals must outsource funds internally or externally to provide teachers with a safe working environment that allows them to demonstrate their best qualitative teaching (Ezeugbor et al., 2018). This research is related to this study because both seek to determine the school operations practices expected of a school manager to ensure that the welfare of the

staff is adequately managed, resulting in their satisfaction in performing their responsibilities.

On the other hand, the school's performance is a significant output of the school operations. One of the measurements of school performance is the School-based Management (SBM). It is a strategy to improve education by transferring significant decision-making authority from state and district offices to individual schools. SBM gives principals, teachers, students, and parents greater control over the education process by giving them responsibility for budget, personnel, and curriculum. (Villanueva & Cruz, 2019).

On this basis, the study decided to focus on school operations of school leaders, particularly in managing the implementation of the K-12 Curriculum. Given the importance of these management competencies in the continuous implementation of the curriculum, school leaders must be allowed to reflect on and determine their practices in the school's operations. And their performance using the prescribed standards.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of school operations of elementary school heads in CALABARZON in the implementation of K-12 Curriculum and performance using the Philippine Professional Standards for School heads with an end view of developing an Enhance Curriculum Management Framework. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following subproblems:

1. What is the demographic profile of elementary school heads in terms of the following: 1.1. Designation; 1.2. Sex; 1.3. Educational Attainment; and 1.4. Length of Service
2. What is the level of school operations of elementary school heads in terms of: 2.1. Leadership and governance.
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of school operations when grouped into school head's profile?
4. What is the level of performance of elementary school heads as to Professional Standards for School Heads in terms of the following Domain: 4.1. leading strategically; 4.2. managing school operations and resources; 4.3. focusing on teaching and learning; 4.4. developing self and others; and 4.5. building connections
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of elementary school heads as to Professional Standards for School Heads when grouped in respondent's demographic profiles?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of school operations and the level of performance of elementary school heads?

Literature Review

School Heads

School heads, as stewards of schools, play a crucial role in ensuring an enabling and supportive environment for effective teaching and learning. Because of their excellent leadership and management, the Department of Education can produce quality teachers and holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st century skills and capable of propelling the country forward. (Department Order No.42, s. 2017)

School heads play an important role in the mentoring process which helps improve teacher motivation, especially the new ones. (Tourniel et al. 2019). While the standards and the training goals for school heads remain context and the policies should encourage all principals and school heads to demonstrate and build mutual relationships with their teachers and other school personnel. School heads and school also have the advantage of having a good relationship outside the school and be a part of networks, clusters, and other professional learning groups and spaces.

The roles of school heads encompass more diverse duties and expectations, ranging from instructional leader to financial manager to policy developer, decision maker, staff mediator, negotiator, and marketer. They are responsible for the overall organizational management and instructional leadership of schools and require specialized skills to lead effectively. A school head is a custodian of school values within the school values, mission, and vision. Yet they continue to lack the systematic support and professional development they need, especially in school operations (Rodriguez et al., 2021)

The concept of leadership implies subordination. It involves interpersonal relationships; more specifically, school heads suggest differential influence among individuals in social, particularly organizational relationships.

All public elementary and secondary schools must have a school principal. A group of them, in accordance with Section 6.1, Rule VI of the Implementing Rules, and Regulations of Republic Act No. 9155 (Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001). The school principal oversees the administrative and educational functions of the school. The school head is expected to possess a strong leadership skills and managerial skills. To become a school principal, one must pass a qualifying test and must have an experience of at least five (5) years in the aggregate as the head teacher, teacher in charge, master teacher I, master teacher II, and teacher III. To become a teacher-in charge, one must have at least three (3) years of teaching experience and undergo a screening process to be conducted in their respective division offices.

According to Asiyai and Akporehe (2023), school heads should equip themselves with managerial skills and long-term experiences necessary in leading the school to meet the goals and objectives, following the duty and responsibility of school heads, and emphasizes

the importance of instructional leadership skills in school leaders for faculty support, and communication with stakeholders and the community.

School Operations

Traditional public-school principals are responsible for more than just teaching and learning. Many former teachers spend most of their time managing non-instructional domains such as fire drills, budgeting, school food, field trips, and sports. As a result, they become increasingly disconnected from both students and, more importantly, teachers' instructional practices. School operations managers oversee all day-to-day operations at their schools. They oversee everything from curriculum to facilities, and they frequently play a crucial role in developing new initiatives or programs to improve the quality of education their institutions provide. School operations managers may also oversee staff management, such as hiring decisions, performance evaluations, and other aspects of employee management.

As a result of the decentralization trends in management settings in education, many schools worldwide have adopted School-based Management as a national education policy. Many education leaders and experts are drawn to School-based Management (SBM) because it produces numerous positive outcomes such as improved student academic performance, increased parental, and community participation in children's education, and, most importantly, empowers local leaders. As a result, the centralized and bureaucratic system was deconstructed and rebuilt to make way for a decentralized management system.

In addition, the school operations and management practices of the school heads are assessed, evaluated, and monitored using School-Based Management (SBM) practices. Their ability and competency in performing their tasks and roles as efficient and effective school leaders would be reflected in each practice they would achieve. In addition, school leaders are responsible for keeping the workplace safe and friendly (Cabigao, 2019). It would entail instilling a sense of camaraderie and mutual respect among teachers-co-teachers and other school personnel. This task is not easy for school leaders, who are sometimes reassigned to different schools because each school is an independent entity with its peculiarities, such as an organizational culture was established before they arrived at the school.

To be successful in their roles within a school district, school leaders must direct several managerial tasks. Major tasks include school management and operational systems, resource management, policies and procedures, distributed leadership, and supervision. Empowering teachers to do tasks and decision-making in their school districts is one of the goals of school-based management. While each school leader may approach the implementation and oversight of each category differently, they must ensure that each component is properly managed. The school operations and management department oversee the day-to-day operations of the schools. On the other side, this is related to school performance. The researcher highlighted the school's success in terms of the four pillars of SBM, which include leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and resource management, in this study.

A school leader must first understand what school-based policies are to understand every situation in the school. School leaders should read all district policy documents. They should become acquainted with their school district's student code of conduct. It may take longer for the school leader to understand the policies if they are new to the district. It may also be advantageous for the school leader to consult with other school leaders or a mentor to understand better the policies in place and how they may impact their ability to make decisions in the school.

Performance Evaluation through Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH)

In line with the commitment of the Department of Education to support the school heads to better perform their roles in school, including the improvement of teacher quality through learner achievement, the PPSSH provides support for professional learning and development, helps identify development needs, and facilitate uniform assessment of school heads performance.

The value of education as a means of achieving success in life is widely acknowledged. It creates many opportunities and assists people in thinking, feeling, and acting in ways that contribute to their success (Caballes & Peregrino, 2021). This was highlighted in an article published by Asian College, which stated that education is a tool that provides people with knowledge, skills, technology, and information that allows them to understand their rights and responsibilities to their families, communities, and country. It broadens one's vision and outlook to see the future.

The role of school principals is one of many factors that have a significant impact on educational quality. School heads play an essential role in ensuring the quality of education provided by the school. It is stressed that learners are at the heart of education, and their full potential must be developed as to thrive in a rapidly changing world. The role of school principals is one of many factors that have a significant impact on educational quality. School heads play an essential role in ensuring the school's educational quality.

As the School Heads are responsible for the overall operations of their schools, they must equip themselves with the necessary skills and competencies that will be their weapon in running their schools and ensuring that quality education is provided. School leaders' competencies and qualifications, such as their educational attainment, training attended, years of experience as a school leader, and position, can all impact on their performance as a school leader. Hence, these factors are always considered, particularly when ranking School heads. However, some studies argue that only a school leader's attitude makes them effective as a school leader.

They function as educational leaders, facilitators, and managers, guiding and managing high-quality instructional practices. School heads are responsible for ensuring that everyone in the schoolwork's effectively, efficiently, and collaboratively and that all aspects are in place. Similarly, influential school leaders are strong educators who focus on central issues such as learning, teaching, and continuous school improvement. School leaders must guide their schools through the goal-setting process, which includes analyzing student achievement data, identifying areas for improvement, and initiating change initiatives (Pepito & Acibar, 2019). The Philippine educational system recognized and supported the influence of school principals in improving educational quality by elevating school performance.

To reflect the accomplishments of his or her office, the school heads complete the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form, or OPCRF. The OPCRF must be accompanied by reports, documents, or other outputs demonstrating actual performance (Lapus, 2007, as cited by Pepito & Acibar, 2021). On the other hand, when it comes to education, the entire community is always concerned about how the school performs. As a result, the government and the Department of Education are evaluating school performance based on their missions and visions. Similarly, school performance is a significant concern for students, parents, teachers, and authorities in many other countries worldwide (DepEd, 2010). As a result, education is everyone's concern in the community.

Consequently, countries worldwide are constantly strengthening their education systems to ensure that every citizen receives a quality education. Quality education is at the heart of personal and community development; its mission is to enable all learners to fully develop their talents and skills and realize their creative potential, including personal responsibility and achievement of personal goals (Alleem, 2018).

Thus, the PPSSH establishes professional standards for a quality school principal. It will serve as a public statement of school leaders' professional accountability. It outlines what school leaders are expected to know, be able to do, and value as they advance in their careers. It establishes a common language for the high-impact leadership expected of school principals to guide individual professional reflections, professional discussions among educational leaders and other stakeholders, and to inform the provision of professional learning and development for school principals.

Furthermore, the professional leadership competencies of school heads/principals serve as school success indicators. Competent school leaders would enable a specific school to meet their performance targets and promote positive school outcomes. In a public [government] school, the school heads are empowered as leaders and managers to direct the implementation and evaluation of all school projects and activities for a given school year. These activities are included in their three-year Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) derived from the School Improvement Plan (SIP).

Methodology

This quantitative study employed a descriptive research design. This design is viewed as appropriate to describe the profile of the respondents related to the level of school operations in the implementation of the k-12 curriculum and the performance level by elementary school heads. In addition, this study also employed a causal-comparative design to compare the level of school operations and the performance level of the school heads based on their profile variables. Comparing variables and finding significant differences among it. Moreover, correlational design has been used to determine the significant relationship between the level of school operations and the performance of school heads.

This research was conducted in the CALABARZON region, with one school division office (SDO) chosen from Cavite, Laguna, Batangas, Rizal, and Quezon Provinces. The participants were Ten (10) schools were selected in each SDO with small, medium, and large categories 50 schools. A standard and self-constructed research questionnaire is the main instrument employed in this study. A questionnaire was crafted as the instrument to gather data for this study. The questionnaire was presented to an expert panel for content review. The suggestions and comments of these experts were considered and incorporated into the research questionnaire. With the revision, it was again presented to the experts who reviewed the research questionnaire. Following experts' approval, the self-crafted research questionnaire was tested for validity and reliability.

Following its validation, the researcher prepared a request letter addressed to the Department of Education (DepEd) CALABARZON Regional Director for approval, then forwarded it to the different Schools Division Superintendents. A division memorandum was requested to include the target school respondents in the research as participants. A Google link was included in the request letters from the regional offices and SDOs to facilitate response consolidation. All communications were linked to the Google Form. Questionnaires were distributed through Google Form and collected on an online basis during first quarter of the academic year 2023. The gathered data were submitted to the statistician for statistical treatment and was treated with utmost confidentiality.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, high importance was placed on ethical consideration. First, permissions were sought, and other communications were sent to the different offices where the research was scheduled to be conducted, including the DepEd CALABARZON Regional Office, the various Schools Division Offices, and, of course, the school heads of respondent schools. Second, permission and signal from the granting institution, Marinduque State College, to perform the survey was considered.

More importantly, the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identity in the data collection, analysis, and reporting of the study findings. Privacy and confidentiality of the interview environment was managed carefully during telephone communication, interview session, data analysis and dissemination of the findings.

Results

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. To answer problem 1 and 3, mean was employed. To answer problem 2 and 4, Two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized. To answer problem 5, Pearson's Product Moment of Correlation was employed.

Table 1. *Level of School Operations*

Indicators	Composite Mean	Int	Rank
Leadership and Governance	2.71	A	1
Curriculum and Instruction	2.56	A	3
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.63	A	2
Management of Resources	2.51	A	4
GRAND MEAN	2.60	A	

Legend: 2.50-3.00 Best (A), 1.50-2.49 Better (B), 0.50-1.49 Good (C)

Table 2. *Significant Difference in the School Operation as to Demography*

Indicators	School Size	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision
Leadership and Governance	Position/Designation	31.07	1.772	0.043	Reject Ho
	Sex	27.43		0.039	
	Length of Service	23.92		0.044	
	Educational Attainment	22.00		0.036	
Curriculum and Instruction	Position/Designation	32.23	0.532	0.007	Reject Ho
	Sex	28.56		0.016	
	Length of Service	29.70		0.032	
	Educational Attainment	30.34		0.077	
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	Position/Designation	34.82	1.043	0.033	Reject Ho
	Sex	33.82		0.041	
	Length of Service	33.46		0.048	
	Educational Attainment	34.67		0.031	
Management of Resources	Position/Designation	31.31	1.446	0.047	Reject Ho
	Sex	33.54		0.053	
	Length of Service	31.38		0.034	
	Educational Attainment	34.55		0.011	

Table 3. *Level of Performance of School Head*

Performance	Composite Mean	Int	Rank
Leading Strategically	4.38	TVME	5
Managing School Operations and Resources	4.54	TVME	4
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	4.65	TVME	3
Developing Self and Others	4.72	TVME	2
Building Connections	4.79	TVME	1
GRAND MEAN	4.58	TVME	

Legend: 4.21-5.00 To a very much extent (TVME) 3.41-4.20 To a much extent (TME) 2.61-3.40 To a fair extent (TFE) 1.81-2.60 To a less extent (TE) 1.00-1.80 To a least extent (TLE)

Table 4. *Significant Difference in the Level of Performance According to Demography*

Indicators	Profile	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision
Leading Strategically	Position/Designation	32.08	3.772	0.263	Failed to Reject Ho
	Sex	35.63		0.144	
	Length of Service	33.22		0.232	
	Educational Attainment	31.00		0.090	
Managing School Operations and Resources	Position/Designation	34.19	0.532	0.347	Failed to Reject Ho
	Sex	37.18		0.213	
	Length of Service	31.70		0.421	
	Educational Attainment	33.23		0.113	
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	Position/Designation	39.60	2.032	0.453	Failed to Reject Ho
	Sex	34.77		0.074	

Developing Self and Others	Length of Service	23.14		0.341	
	Educational Attainment	26.06		0.366	
	Position/Designation	38.31		0.543	
	Sex	36.86	0.479	0.543	Failed to
	Length of Service	39.35		0.532	Reject Ho
Building Connections	Educational Attainment	37.57		0.073	
	Position/Designation	33.04		0.329	
	Sex	33.56	3.211	0.322	Failed to
	Length of Service	32.75		0.243	Reject Ho
	Educational Attainment	30.76		0.132	

Table 5. Relationship Between the Level of School Operations and School Heads' Performance

Variable 1	Variable 2	p-Value	Rho	Int	Decision
LG	CI	0.624	-0.300	NS	Accept Ho
LG	ACI	0.505	-0.400	NS	Accept Ho
LG	MR	0.188	-0.700	NS	Accept Ho
LG	LS	0.285	0.600	NS	Accept Ho
LG	MSO	0.624	-0.300	NS	Accept Ho
LG	FTL	0.104	0.800	NS	Accept Ho
LG	DSO	0.188	-0.700	NS	Accept Ho
LG	BC	0.505	0.400	NS	Accept Ho
CI	ACI	0.285	-0.600	NS	Accept Ho
CI	MR	0.104	0.800	NS	Accept Ho
CI	LS	0.037	.900*	S	Reject Ho
CI	MSO	0.104	-0.800	NS	Accept Ho
CI	FTL	0.624	-0.300	NS	Accept Ho
CI	DSO	0.624	-0.300	NS	Accept Ho
CI	BC	1.000	0.000	NS	Accept Ho
ACI	MR	0.873	-0.100	NS	Accept Ho
ACI	LS	0.747	0.200	NS	Accept Ho
ACI	MSO	0.037	.900*	S	Reject Ho
ACI	FTL	0.505	-0.400	NS	Accept Ho
ACI	DSO	0.391	0.500	NS	Accept Ho
ACI	BC	0.747	-0.200	NS	Accept Ho
MR	LS	0.037	.900*	S	Reject Ho
MR	MSO	0.624	-0.300	NS	Accept Ho
MR	FTL	0.188	-0.700	NS	Accept Ho
MR	DSO	0.747	0.200	NS	Accept Ho
MR	BC	0.873	0.100	NS	Accept Ho
LS	MSO	0.391	0.500	NS	Accept Ho
LS	FTL	0.285	0.600	NS	Accept Ho
LS	DOS	0.873	0.100	NS	Accept Ho
LS	BC	0.747	0.200	NS	Accept Ho
MSO	FTL	0.624	-0.300	NS	Accept Ho
MSO	DOS	0.188	0.700	NS	Accept Ho
MSO	BC	0.873	-0.100	NS	Accept Ho
FTL	DSO	0.188	-0.700	NS	Accept Ho
FTL	BC	0.505	0.400	NS	Accept Ho
DSO	BC	0.873	-0.100	NS	Accept Ho

Discussion

This study shed light on the level of school operations of elementary school heads in the CALABARZON region in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources. School heads manifested “Best performance in the level of operations with a grand mean of 2.60 with the indicator “leadership and governance” as the highest. The findings shows that there is statistically significant difference in the school operations of the school heads based on the demographic profile. In the level of performance using the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads, the findings shows that all the five indicators were similarly assessed as “To a Very Much Extent” with a grand mean of 4.58. with indicator “Developing Self and Others” as the highest. The statistical analysis conducted in the level of performance in terms of leading strategically, managing school operations and resources, focusing on teaching and learning, developing self and others, and building connections and considering the demographic factors of the respondents. The fact that the p-values are greater than 0.05 in each area indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the performance of elementary school heads based on this demographic profile. The orthogonal relationships between the variables of the level of school operations and resources and school heads’ performance the Spearman Rho Rank Correlation found that there is a significant relationship between curriculum and instruction and leading

strategically. This indicates that the curriculum and instruction depend on the leadership skills of a leader. Further, curriculum and instruction affected how the school heads led the school.

Conclusion

Majority of the respondents were principal I, female, with master's degree holders, and with 6-10 years' experience as school heads. School heads evaluated across dimensions in the school operations including leadership, governance, curriculum, instruction, accountability, and resource management. The "Best" performance level was observed in these areas. Rejection of null hypotheses suggests significant performance differences in various dimensions. There is a significant relationship between the level of school operations and the school heads' performance. Notably a strong correlation was found between curriculum and instruction and strategic leadership. Further, the curriculum and instruction affected how the school heads led the school. In short, educational outcome depends on the leadership style of the school heads. Challenges on the school operations and analysis and prioritization drive continuous improvement, with alignment to existing research enhancing decision-making. Addressing operational challenges enhances overall school system effectiveness. Elementary school heads exhibit commitment to delivering an enhanced educational experience. Proactive approaches to leadership, curriculum, accountability, and resource challenges align with the best practices for quality education and improvement. The study proposed Enhanced Curriculum Management Framework as a strategic guide based on study results.

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